

Studies on Benzenesulphonamidomethyl Benzimidazoles Part VII. Copper(II), Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) Chelates of Benzenesulphonamido-ethylene 2,2'-Dibenzimidazole.

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Complex compounds of Cu(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) with the ligand benzenesulphonamido-ethylene 2,2'-dibenzimidazole (RH) have been prepared. They are Cu(R) (CH_3COO), Cu(R) $_2$ ·3H₂O, Cu(R) $_2$, Co(R) (CH_3COO), Co(R) (OH), Co(R) $_2$ ·4H₂O, Co(R) $_2$, Ni(R) $_2$ ·5H₂O and Ni(R) $_2$. Attempts have been made to assign their probable structures with the aid of magnetic data, electronic and ir spectral data.

COMPLEXATION of sulphonamidobenzimidazoles with some metal ions have been initiated in this laboratory^{1,2}. Various ligands of this type have been synthesised by us^{3,4} and studied as metal complexing agents in (1:1) water-dioxan^{5,6}. The present paper describes the isolation and characterization of Cu(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes of benzenesulphonamido-ethylene 2,2'-dibenzimidazole⁴ (RH).

Experimental

The compound (RH) was prepared by condensing N-benzenesulphonyl L(-) aspartic acid⁷ with *o*-phenylene diamine in presence of boiling 4N hydrochloric acid⁸. The compound RH, 2H₂O was purified by crystallization from warm aqueous ethanol and obtained as white shining crystals⁴. It lost two molecules of water on heating several hours at 110°. No sharp melting point was obtained but melted in the range 130°-140° and quickly solidified which decomposed above 250°. Complex compounds of RH with Cu(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) were isolated as described below. Their analytical data are stated in Table I.

Cu(II) Complexes :

Cu(R)(CH₃COO) : On mixing ethanolic solutions of cupric acetate and RH in the molar ratio 1 : 1, a green solution was obtained, from which a light-green compound began to separate. It was filtered, washed with ethanol and air-dried. The same compound was also prepared by adding acetic acid to an ethanolic solution of Cu(R) $_2$. The compound insoluble in water, ethanol and chloroform but soluble in DMSO.

Cu(R) $_2$ ·3H₂O and Cu(R) $_2$: The ligand RH (4 g) was dissolved in 100 ml of ethanol and the pH of the solution was raised to about 12 with a strong aqueous solution of NaOH. Cupric chloride dihydrate (0.7g) was dissolved in minimum quantity of water and added to the ligand solution. A deep green solution was obtained. The solution was shaken with distilled chloroform (50 ml) in a separatory funnel. The chloroform layer was separated and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On evaporation of dried chloroform extract, shining green crystals were obtained. The crystals were collected, washed with chloroform and air-dried. It is highly soluble in ethanol, DMF, DMSO, etc. but insoluble in water. On heating the trihydrate at 110° to a constant weight the anhydrous compound Cu(R) $_2$ was obtained.

Co(II) Complexes

Co(R)(CH₃COO) : An ethanolic solution of cobalt acetate (0.01 mole) was added to a hot ethanolic solution of RH (0.01 mole). A deep pink colour developed and shining pink crystals began to separate. They were collected, washed with ethanol and air-dried. The compound is insoluble in water and ethanol but soluble in DMSO.

Co(R) (OH) : Cobalt chloride hexahydrate (0.75g) in 10 ml of water was added to 50 ml ethanolic solution of RH (1.5 g). A deep green solution was obtained. On adjusting pH of the solution to ~7 with a NaOH solution, a violet compound separated. It was dissolved in DMSO and reprecipitated by adding ethanol, filtered washed with ethanol and dried at 110° to a constant weight. It is soluble in DMF and DMSO but insoluble in water and ethanol.

Co(R) $_2$ ·4H₂O and Co(R) $_2$: The ligand RH (2.5g) was dissolved in ethanol (100 ml). Cobalt nitrate hexahydrate (0.75g) was dissolved in a minimum amount of water and added to the ligand solution. The pH of the solution was adjusted to ~9 with a solution of

NaOH. A deep violet solution was obtained. The resulting solution was shaken with chloroform in a separatory funnel and the compound $\text{Co(R)}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained following the similar procedure as in the case of $\text{Cu(R)}_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$. It is highly soluble in ethanol, DMF, DMSO but insoluble in water. On heating the compound to a constant weight at 110° , the anhydrous compound Co(R)_2 was obtained.

Ni(II) Complexes

Ni(R)₂ · 5H₂O and Ni(R)₂: The ligand RH(2.5g) was dissolved in ethanol (100 ml) and a strong aqueous solution of NaOH was added to raise the pH to ~12. Nickel nitrate hexahydrate (0.75g) in 10 ml water was added to the ligand solution. A deep purple colour was developed. It was extracted with chloroform following similar procedure as in the case of Cu(II) or Co(II) compound. On evaporation of the purple chloroform extract, light green crystals of $\text{Ni(R)}_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were obtained. The compound is insoluble in water, ethanol but soluble in DMSO giving a deep purple solution. It was also prepared by treating an ethanolic solution (100 ml) of nickel acetate (1 g) and RH (5.5 g) with strong ammonia solution (2 ml) and the resulting mixture was warmed, treated with water (10 ml) and kept overnight. Shining light green crystals of $\text{Ni(R)}_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ separated. On heating the pentahydrate at 110° to a constant weight, the light rose-red anhydrous compound Ni(R)_2 was obtained.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements of all the compounds were made at room temperature. Results after diamagnetic corrections⁹ are included in Table 1. The electronic spectra in mull, ethanol, DMF & DMSO of the complexes were measured at room temperature. Data are stated in Table 2. I.R. spectra in KBr matrices of the metal chelates were recorded. The tentative assignments¹⁰⁻¹³ of some of the vibrations were made (Table 3). The corresponding ir data⁴ of RH are also included in Table 3 for comparison.

Discussion

Potentiometric studies⁸ in (1 : 1) water-dioxan on the complex formation of RH have indicated the formation of (1 : 1) and (1 : 2) complexes with Cu(II) and Co(II) and (1 : 1) complex with Ni(II). Both (1 : 1) and (1 : 2) complexes of Cu(II) and Co(II) have been isolated under suitable conditions; (1 : 2) complex of Ni(II) has also been prepared following similar procedure as in (1 : 2) complexes of Cu(II) and Co(II), though it was not possible to follow potentiometrically due to precipitation after completion of (1 : 1) complex formation. Attempts to prepare (1 : 1) Ni(II) complex using various solvents were made but the compound could not be isolated.

The ligand RH has two imidazole nuclei and one sulphonamido group—the possible sites on complex formation. Thus it behaves as a monoprotic tridentate ligand.

For characterization of complex compound, magnetic data^{14,15} are a useful tool for many cases. The magnetic moment values of Cu(II) are generally ranging from 1.8 to 2.2 B.M.^{9,14}. In the present case the observed values are in the said region. By magnetic measurements characterization of structures of Cu(II) complexes is not always possible.

The octahedral Ni(II) complexes should have magnetic moments ranging from 2.9 to 3.4 B.M. depending on the magnitude of orbital contribution, and tetrahedral Ni(II) complexes have moments ranging from 3.5 to 4.2 B.M.⁹ In the present cases Ni(II) complexes are found to have magnetic moments from 3.12-3.21 B.M., evidently they have distorted octahedral structures.

The high spin octahedral Co(II) complexes have the magnetic moments ranging from 4.7. to 5.2 B.M. and the tetrahedral complexes have generally in the

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND SOME PROPERTIES OF METAL CHELATES

Compounds	Colour	% Metal Found (Reqd)	% Nitrogen Found (Reqd.)	% Loss at 110° Found (Reqd.)	Temperature °K	μ_{eff} B. M.
$\text{Cu(R)(CH}_3\text{COO)}$	yellowish green	11.61 (11.80)	12.92 (12.99)	—	294	1.75
$\text{Cu(R)}_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	yellowish green	6.56 (6.69)	—	6.15 (5.69)	301	1.86
Cu(R)_2	yellowish green	7.00 (7.10)	15.70 (15.63)	—	301	1.72
$\text{Co(R)(CH}_3\text{COO)}$	pink	11.30 (11.04)	12.96 (13.11)	—	295	4.47
Co(R)(OH)	violet	12.02 (11.78)	14.30 (14.22)	—	301	4.31
$\text{Co(R)}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	violet	6.30 (6.12)	—	7.66 (7.48)	299	3.92
Co(R)_2	violet	6.75 (6.62)	15.60 (15.71)	—	301	3.75
$\text{Ni(R)}_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	light green	5.80 (5.99)	—	8.90 (9.18)	294	3.12
Ni(R)_2	light rose-red	6.30 (6.59)	15.79 (15.71)	—	294	3.21

TABLE 2—SPECTRAL DATA OF THE METAL CHELATES IN THE VISIBLE REGION WITH SOME OF THEIR ASSIGNMENTS

Compounds	$\lambda_{\text{EtoH max}}$ (nm)	log ϵ	$\lambda_{\text{DMSO max}}$ (nm)	log ϵ	$\lambda_{\text{DMF max}}$ (nm)	log ϵ	$\lambda_{\text{Mull max}}$ (nm)	O.D. in arbitrary Units	Probable assignments		
Cu(R)CH ₃ COO)	633	2.34	660-670	2.02	660-670	0.690			
Cu(R) ₂ 3H ₂ O	680	2.19	650	1.84	690-710	1.84	670-680	0.486			
Co(R)(OH)	900(sh)	1.30	908(sh)	1.57	} $4T_{1g} \rightarrow 2E_g$ $\rightarrow 4A_{2g}$ (F) $\rightarrow 4T_{1g}$ (P)		
			575	2.51	585	2.60	590	0.499			
			562	2.52	570	2.61			
			506(sh)	2.08	512(sh)	2.34	510	0.480			
Co(R)(CH ₃ COO)	900(sh)	1.18	910(sh)	1.07	} $4T_{1g} \rightarrow 2E_g$ $\rightarrow 4A_{2g}$ (F) $\rightarrow 4T_{1g}$ (P)		
			577	2.30	585-599	2.24			
			565	2.35	570	2.26	530	0.33			
			508(sh)	1.93	495(sh)	1.88			
Co(R) ₂ 4H ₂ O	900	1.62	900	1.32	900	1.43	900	0.420	} $4T_{1g} \rightarrow 2E_g$ $\rightarrow 4A_{2g}$ (F) $\rightarrow 4T_{1g}$ (P)		
			582	2.19	595	2.39		590	0.601
			570	2.61	560	2.21	570	2.41		560	0.632
			538	2.17	5.45	2.37		533	0.577
			490	1.88
Ni(R) ₂ 5H ₂ O	760	0.71	765	1.38	780	0.399	} $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 1F_g$ $\rightarrow 3T_{1g}$ (D) $\rightarrow 3T_{1g}$ (F)		
			560	1.11	550	1.72	
			495	1.11	500	1.78		510	0.443
Ni(R) ₂	780-800	0.648	} $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 1E_g$ $\rightarrow 3T_{1g}$ (D)		
				510	0.733

TABLE 3—THE I. R. FREQUENCIES OF INTEREST OF RH AND ITS METAL CHELATES ALONG WITH THE TENTATIVE ASSIGNMENTS. Frequencies (cm⁻¹)

Compounds	O-H, N-H and C-H stretches	C=N stretches	Lattice water	-SO ₂ N< and II & I	Heterocyclic ring breathing modes
RH 2H ₂ O	3330 s 3060 s 2960 s 2925 s	1615 w	1590 w	1373 m 1150 m	890 w 825 w 765 w
Cu(R)(CH ₃ COO)	2925 s 3500 m 3060 m 2910 w	1620 m	[1610 m] [*] [1330 m]	1270 s 1135 m	845 s 745 m 840 m
Cu(R) ₂ 3H ₂ O	3550 m 3250 m 3060 w	1620 m	1530 m	1270 s 1135 m	740 s 835 m 790 m 735 s
Co(R)(CH ₃ COO)	3540 w 3075 m 2910 s 2860 s	1600 s	[1580 s, 1375 m] [*]	1260 s 1130 s	740 s 835 m 790 m 735 s
Co(R) ₂ 4H ₂ O	3530 m 3365 m 3060 m	1620 m	1580 s	1270 s 1135 s	840 m 790 m 740 s 830 w
Co(R)(OH)	3200 w 3060 w 2900 w	1620 w		1270 s 1135 s	740 s 840 m 780 m 740 s
Ni(R) ₂ 5H ₂ O	3620 w 3200 m 3060 m 2920 m	1620 m	1540 m	1270 m 1138 s	740 s 840 m 780 m 740 s

s=strong ; m =medium ; w=weak.
* = COO⁻ antisymmetrical and symmetrical stretches.

range 4.1-4.8 B.M.¹⁶. They have higher magnetic moment values than spin only values due to high orbital contributions. In the cases of (1:1) complexes of Co(II) magnetic moment 4.31 B.M. for Co(R)(OH) and 4.47 B.M. for Co(R)(CH₃COO) are obtained. So the tetrahedral configuration may be assigned to them. However lower magnetic moment values are no definite criteria for adjusting the geometry of Co(II) complexes^{17,18}. The complexes Co(R)₂ and Co(R)₂·4H₂O have anomalous magnetic moments 3.75 and 3.92 B.M. respectively. The magnetic moments of these Co(II) complexes are much lower than that usually observed for spin-free octahedral complexes, which may be due to the presence of some low-spin species or contamination of some Co(III) complexes. The partial oxidation of Co(II) to Co(III) has been observed in the cases of ligands containing N atoms as donors¹⁶.

Electronic spectra of Cu(II) complexes in mull and also in various solvents support octahedral stereochemistry. The maxima observed at 633-670 nm and 650-710 nm for Cu(R)(CH₃COO) and Cu(R)₂·3H₂O are due to *d-d* transitions¹⁶. The position of *d-d* bands is a useful indication of the degree of tetragonal distortion¹⁹. Data (Table 2) show that Cu(R)(CH₃COO) has a much greater tetragonally distorted structure than that of Cu(R)₂·3H₂O. The Co(II) complexes have exhibited three *d-d* bands expected for octahedral ones. However, a splitting of the band corresponding to the transition ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴A_{2g} (F) has been observed in the case of Co(R)₂·4H₂O—not only in various solvents but also in mull spectra. And in the mull spectra of Co(R)(CH₃COO) and Co(R)(OH) all *d-d* bands are not observed. The spectral assignments of Ni(II) complexes could not be made with absolute certainty. However, positions and intensities²⁰ are helpful in deducing tentative assignments which are shown in Table 2. A splitting of the band corresponding to the transition ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (F) has been observed.

The ir spectral data show shift in —SO₂N< stretching frequencies (band I) at 1372 cm⁻¹ in the ligand RH to lower frequencies 1260-1270 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. The shifts are closely comparable to that in the salts of the type Na₂Cu(R_t)₂ where R_tH₂ = *N-p*-toluenesulphonyl glycine²¹. Therefore it is likely that these are associated with the ionization of the imido-hydrogen of sulphonamido group. The C=N stretch at 1600 cm⁻¹ of the ligand is shifted to higher frequencies at 1620 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes except Co(R)(CH₃COO) where no change has been observed. However the heterocyclic breathing modes 890, 825, 765 cm⁻¹ of the ligand are shifted to lower frequencies on complex formation. They may be regarded as evidences of bonding of nitrogen of —SO₂N< as well as basic nitrogen (tertiary one) in the imidazole ring to

metal. In the complexes of imidazole derivatives the fact that coordination takes place through tertiary nitrogen, has been confirmed by X-ray crystallographic studies^{22,23} on structures of Cu (4-MeIz) (NO₃)₂ and Zn (Iz)₂Cl₂ (where 4-MeIz = 4-methylimidazole and Iz = imidazole). The presence of acetato group in Cu(R)(CH₃COO) and Co(R)(CH₃COO) has been indicated by ir band at 1610, 1330 cm⁻¹ and 1580, 1375 cm⁻¹ respectively being COO⁻ antisymmetrical and symmetrical stretches.

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